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Aircraft Cabin Air – Neurotoxicity: Update and in-Depth Analysis

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Abstract

Purpose: The major objective of this study was to explore for possible common abnormal quantitative EEG (qEEG) and Low-Resolution Electromagnetic Tomography (LORETA) measures in a self-selected population experiencing health problems related to cabin air contamination.

Methodology: The EEG was recorded from 19 scalp locations, according to the International 10–20 System, from 70 participants ranging in age from 25 to 67 years. The majority were pilots and flight attendants with 2 to 42 years flying experience who were still active or non-active for 6 months up to 22 years. A small group of the participants were either frequent flyers or ground crew. Individuals were recorded during eyes-closed (ECB) and eyes-opened (EOB) baselines. Each ECB recording was visually inspected and classified according to the percent time of alpha appearance and distribution across the scalp. QEEG analysis was performed, calculating global absolute and relative powers for the delta, theta, alpha and beta bands and inter- and intra-hemispheric amplitude asymmetries, coherences and phase lag. LORETA current sources were also computed from 1 to 30 Hz.

Findings: A comparative inter-individual study of the EEG, qEEG and LORETA resulted in identifying 4 distinct groups. Each participant could be assigned to a particular group based on their percent time of alpha appearance and distribution across the scalp in the ECB EEG and alpha band peak frequency source power distribution. Group 1 can be characterized by a dominant posterior alpha rhythm and shows a maximum alpha band peak frequency source power distribution at the right postcentral and right superior temporal areas. Group 2 can be characterized by a subdominant posterior alpha rhythm and shows a maximum alpha band peak frequency source power distribution at the right postcentral and right superior temporal areas. Group 3 is represented by a rare or absent alpha presence and shows no qEEG or LORETA abnormal activity in the alpha band. Group 4 is represented by a diffuse alpha activity and a maximum alpha band peak frequency source power distribution in the anterior cingulate. Group 1 and 2 contains the largest number of subjects (82.9%), followed by group 3 with 11.4% of the subjects and group 4 with 5.7% of the subjects.

Discussion: These results raise a lot of questions that can be summarized under two main headings; where do these results come from and what effect can they have? Subjects exposed to aircraft cabin air can experience a varied number of symptoms. This research focuses on how the affected cortical areas may contribute to several of these symp-

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toms. For this we look at three major brain systems or networks: cognitive brain networks, central vestibular system and language system. First, the areas with the maximum source power distribution of group 1, 2 and 4 belong to the three core cognitive brain networks. From this viewpoint we can expect cognitive dysfunctions that can vary according which areas and the number of areas that are affected in these networks. Secondly, the areas with the maximum source power distribution of group 1 and 2 are part of the central vestibular system in the non-dominant right-hemisphere. This not only means that balance issues can arise but also high-level cortical dysfunctions involving spatial cognition, including self-body perception, verticality perception, orientation, navigation and spatial memory. Thirdly, when looking at the language system and the results we would not expect any language related symptoms since language is in the dominant left-hemisphere for the majority of people, even in left-handed people. Research has shown that handedness determined by questionnaires are not a reliable indicator to determine the laterality of language and that language representation may be best considered as continuous rather than dichotomous. MRI DTI tractography studies have demonstrated that mapping cortical pathways is a better, non-invasive method, to determine laterality of language and has shown that language can also be bilateral; either bilateral left dominant or symmetrical. In these latter cases we can expect language reception and understanding dysfunctions for subjects in group 1 and 2. In summary this can help to explain the variability of symptoms across subjects which depends not only on the number of areas affected but also on the laterality of language and vestibular system. To try and answer where these results come from a search of literature related to the cholinergic system was conducted, since it has been established by many authors that exposure to organophosphates, which affect the cholinergic system, are present in aircraft cabin air. Many older experimental studies have shown that acetylcholine modulates the alpha rhythm. In small doses the frequency and amplitude of alpha increase, while a large dose suppresses the alpha activity. Studies on accidental exposure of organophosphate based pesticides have shown that in the acute phase acetylcholine in the blood is increased and that the EEG shows an absence of alpha activity. In the recovery phase the blood level of acetylcholine decreases to normal levels while a gradual return of alpha activity is observed. These findings are consistent with the qEEG results showing variation in alpha power and frequency, and the presence of or absence of abnormal current source density is related to the peak alpha frequency. Other studies on the distribution of cholinergic components seem to indicate a relationship between maximum regional distribution and maximum alpha band peak frequency source power distribution. Histochemical studies illustrates that the maximal regional distribution of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) corresponds to the maximum source power in group 1 and 2. A recent [18F]FEOBV PET tracer study illustrates that the maximal regional distribution of the vesicular acetylcholine transporter (VAcHT) corresponds to the maximum source power in group 4. Further, a clinical example of a frequent flyer seems to indicate that continued exposure over a period of 6 years leads to changes in the EEG, qEEG and LORETA. Initially this subject showed characteristics typical of group 1 and later on characteristics of group 3.

Significance: These results in combination with other studies provide support for biological probability of cholinergic dysfunction due to exposure of organophosphates leading to dose dependent neurophysiological changes consistent with current findings and related cognitive, language and vestibular dysfunctions.

Research Limitations: In spite of the fact that this study presents interesting findings consistent with other research into the cholinergic system and its dysfunctions, it has its limitations. Despite the fact that it suggests a possible dose dependent relationship, there is the lack of available data on the levels to which each member of this population was exposed. In order to further explain the variability of symptoms additional analysis of the data is needed to relate the nature and degree of symptoms to the extent of areas affected for each individual. This will however have its limitations due to a lack of reliable information on the laterality of language and vestibular system.

Keywords

EEG, QEEG, LORETA, acetylcholine, acetylcholinesterase, vesicular, transporter, cholinergic system, neurotransmission

List of Symbols

Ach	Acetylcholine
AchE	Acetylcholinesterase
DTI	Diffusion Tensor Imaging
ECB	Eyes-Closed Baseline
EEG	Electroencephalography
EOB	Eyes-Opened Baseline
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
LORETA	Low-Resolution Electromagnetic Tomography
QEEG	Quantified Electroencephalography
VACHT	Vesicular acetylcholine transporter
[18F]FEOBV	18F-fluoroethoxybenzovesamicol